
Human Resource Management in the Hospitality Sector

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Human resources, or more formally, human assets, are an organization's largest expense for most hospitality organizations. In hotels, payroll is usually the biggest expense driver, second only to material costs in bars and restaurants. Furthermore, the human resources department of a corporation is usually the first point of contact for customers. The effective management of these human resources is therefore essential to the enterprise's success.

Key words: staff, incentives, growth, motivation, and hospitality.

Introduction

Despite numerous economic ups and downs since the mid-1900s, the world's most developed nations have experienced numerous profound and extensive social transformations. Without a doubt, the most significant has been a significant increase in economic prosperity, which has raised living standards for the vast majority of those residing and employed in these nations. Increased productivity and a workforce redistribution from the primary and secondary sectors into service industries and, increasingly emblematic of the twenty-first century, knowledge (information) industries and occupations have been part of these shifts.

Numerous societal developments are associated with the hotel industry, and these changes hold tremendous relevance for the operators within the sector. These include higher disposable incomes, more leisure time (though reports suggest that this trend is reversing in some countries), easier and less expensive travel, and longer lifespans as a result of better lifestyles and access to healthcare, which leads to growing populations and demographic restructuring. In addition, people's behavior is being shaped and informed by the media in all of its forms as never before.

Naturally, when compared to other industries, it is understandable that some parts of the hospitality industry may not be desirable. Some obstacles are inherent and mostly unavoidable, such needing to work on the weekends, in the nights, and on bank holidays. However, diligent management effort can undoubtedly lessen or eliminate other issues. These issues include needless split-shift work, employees' reliance on tips, managers' unwillingness to involve staff in decisions that have an impact on their working lives, and employees' ignorance of pay calculation and service fee distribution techniques. Numerous studies have brought attention to these issues, which, along with certain management beliefs and methods, surely account for a large portion of the labor issues facing the sector. For instance, many managers and companies still today anticipate that all workers, Researchers have discovered methods and strategies to tap into what they perceive to be an innate drive for labor. And employers need to acknowledge this role in the hospitality sector. Workers expect competitive job circumstances and motivational management styles if they are to stay and grow, and the staffing issues in the business will not go away if these are not provided.

Many of the top hotel chains have internationalized as a result of the growing demand for tourism and international travel services, which is a global trend. Employers in the Croatian hospitality sector have to deal with the effect that many prospective workers are now searching for work abroad. In many cases, international visitors to the UK during this time come to learn English.

Naturally, the sector is reacting to significant shifts on the demand side of the business, or the consumer side. Merely demographic shifts, such the proportion and quantity of older people growing, have led to requests for more items meeting their needs, and the decline in the youth population is causing issues with the labor market as well as demand. Changes in eating patterns among the younger population—a move toward "grazing," for instance—have opened up chances for a wide variety of fast food restaurants. A variety of new goods and a corresponding rise in vegetarianism are also the result of the shift to healthier eating.

A dissection of the conventional socioeconomic use of certain catering products is most likely important. Most products are no longer used only by members of specific socioeconomic classes. Rather than being influenced by the socioeconomic category, the use of catering products is now more heavily influenced by the event (behaviourally determined).

1. Human Resource Management

For the majority of hospitality businesses, an organization's human resources, or more formally, human assets, are one of the biggest expenses. Payroll is typically the largest expense factor in hotels, ranking second only to material costs in restaurants and bars. Additionally, a company's human resources department typically serves as its initial point of contact with clients. Therefore, the enterprise's success depends on the efficient administration of these human resources. Line managers, who are frequently also the company's owners, oversee the employees in smaller businesses. Human resource or personnel managers support line managers in larger organizations with staff management difficulties.

An organization's overall policy, which will include several components, will typically include human resource policies. How important they are to the overall policy or to a sub policy may be a good way to gauge how much an organization appreciates its people and their ability to fulfill human resource or personnel functions.

The decisions made by management almost always have an impact on the employees of the company, either more or less. Most choices are made within the stated or tacit policy framework of an organization. Policies serve as the foundation or set of rules for managerial decisions and reflect the objectives, goals, values, or intents of an organization. Policies, which are frequently referred to as "mission statements," can be documented, as many bigger organizations do. As an alternative, they might just be deduced from choices made. Some businesses in the hospitality and catering sectors, like McDonald's, have a policy of only working with specific product categories. Some businesses, like Accor and Whitbread, have a policy of operating in multiple market sectors.

The management can make judgments on where to expand, what to divest, and how to expand—through organic growth, franchising, or merger and acquisition—with the help of these rules.

1.1 Personnel management as a specialist function

Since personnel management is a relatively recent specialization within management, it differs greatly from more established and older specialties like management accounting in terms of its expert role and description. Its definitions and responsibilities are also more ambiguous because of its strong reliance on the social sciences.

Managers who have to "make the profits" often view the people manager as little more than a cost center or the company's social conscience, especially in the private sector. This shouldn't be the case, as it is important to acknowledge that the majority of organizations have two primary roles: one is to accomplish "group goals," such as raising sales or profits or, in the case of the public sector, providing services; the other is to perform "group maintenance," which is the responsibility of forming and upholding the group in order for it to accomplish its objectives. Personnel managers guarantee working circumstances that draw in, hold on to, inspire, and secure the commitment of the right workforce, helping management accomplish their goals in the most efficient way possible.

1.2 Human resource policies

That being said, human resource policies do not emerge out of thin air. They serve as a representation of an organization's ideals and management style. Human resource policies ought to be dynamic, both causing and responding to shifts in the organization's and the workforce's behavior. A personnel department's ability to contribute to the creation of human resource policies will largely depend on where it now stands within the company. However, assessing the degree of risk associated with the job is frequently a good way to gauge its relevance.

1.3 People at work

The social sciences, which focus on examining the interactions between individuals, groups of individuals, and their surroundings, include the study of people in the workplace. The acquired knowledge can be applied primarily in two ways: first, to comprehend and anticipate changes (i.e., to concentrate on "content"), and second, to effect change (i.e., to concentrate on "process"). From the work of behavioral scientists, and Abraham Maslow in particular, it is crucial to conclude that humans are satisfaction-seeking animals driven primarily by biological needs. Managers in the hotel and catering industries should be more aware of this than most others. Furthermore, unlike the majority of animals, humans have additional needs that mostly relate to social interaction once their biological demands are met. The need for status, safety, power, and other external markers of success are manifestations of this. It's possible that most people are unaware of these desires that propel or inspire them. But if management can identify these motivators, they can act accordingly to make sure that these forces may be leveraged for the benefit of the company and the individual.

2. Recruitment

The hospitality sector seems to be having issues hiring because of its bad reputation as an employer. Resolutions from the International Hotel and Restaurants Association in Israel in 1995 and the Netherlands in 1999 have brought attention to issue on a global scale, stating that national associations ought to take the lead in enhancing the industry's reputation as an employer.

2.1 Primary labor market

People who are dedicated to an industry, sometimes even a specific sector within it, through education, training, and experience make up the primary labor market. These work in the hospitality sector and include hall porters, cooks, hotel receptionists, hotel managers, and cocktail bar employees. These individuals hope to advance in the field, and frequently they see prospects both domestically and globally. Consequently, a large number of these individuals are mobile in terms of both geography and organization.

2.2 Secondary Labor Market

On the other side, those with useful talents for an employer but who might not be dedicated to a profession in a specific field make up the secondary labor market. It's likely that they value a place of residence more than a career. Housewives, students, and unskilled workers who choose to work in a given field primarily to make ends meet rather than because they have a strong passion for it are typically found in the secondary labor market. People with talents that may be applicable to numerous industries, such as secretaries, maintenance personnel, bookkeepers, and accountants, are also included in the secondary labor market.

2.3 Discrimination

Regardless of the motivation behind hiring, plans must be created within the framework of employment laws, which address matters like hiring women and children, discrimination based on sex, age, or ethnicity, and hiring disabled individuals.

Apart from the legally mandated requirements to refrain from discriminating on the basis of gender, ethnicity, or disability, some companies choose to uphold this policy even in other contexts, such as when it comes to age discrimination. In any case, employers may find that discrimination based on age is no longer feasible given the demographic increase in the average age of the Croatian population and the growing importance of older age groups as a source of labor in the future, even though the employers' forum on age reported in 1999 that not much real progress was being made in changing attitudes toward the employment of older people.

2.4 The recruitment process

The process of recruiting aims to draw in qualified candidates from whom the best fit may be chosen for a certain position. It depends on having access to the right data, such as a personnel specification, an understanding of the

labor market, and a job or role description. A successful candidate is appointed at the conclusion of the process, which began with the creation of a personnel specification based on a job description or job specification.

2.5 Personnel specification

A "personnel specification," which is a description of the kind of person most likely to be able to perform the job as stated by the job description, can be prepared from the job description. The specifics of a personnel specification will vary depending on how sophisticated an organization is.

2.6 Internal recruitment

Promoting or moving current staff is always the first step in filling a post. Bringing in new hires over current employees can lead to a great deal of frustration, even though this is frequently done to minimize disruption to the company. Unfortunately, the long-term effects are even more detrimental since some members of the organization may leave or behave in other unacceptable ways as a result of having their dreams crushed.

2.7 External recruitment

If none of the current employees are suitable, the next course of action is to go to the labor market. Much issues start here, and this is also where much money and effort can be squandered. Among the many and diverse methods of hiring are:-

- Newspapers: national, local and trade
- Agencies
- Executive selection and management consultants
- Posters
- Colleges
- The armed forces
- The internet

3. The Selection Process

One of a manager's main duties is to take the initiative, but in order to accomplish this, he or she must gather and analyze data in order to draw conclusions that will guide the appropriate course of action. People use their judgment abilities more and perform routine and supervisory jobs less as they advance up the management hierarchy. Actually, the majority of a senior manager's work should be focused on developing systems that facilitate improved decision-making and making decisions that carry out actions. The entire process of choosing employees is related to this expertise.

Selection processes aim to forecast an individual's performance in a specific job or, in the event of many vacancies, the job in which they have the most chance of succeeding. The majority of selection techniques are "historical in nature," meaning they forecast an individual's future performance based on their history performance.

4. Training

An individual needs information, skills, and attitudes in order to perform a job effectively. These are the three essential components. With the right instruction, any of these can be enhanced or developed. On the other hand, every component requires a distinct training strategy. For instance, discussions, lectures, and movies can be used to teach knowledge, but they are nearly useless for teaching the second component, which is knife handling abilities. Practice is essential in this situation. Even with well-founded instruction, the third component—a person's attitudes—is the hardest to convey or alter, and training personnel must possess a thorough understanding of human behavior. Techniques for training in this area could include conversations, role-playing, and case studies. Many behavioral experts do agree, however, that it is preferable to choose individuals with the proper attitudes rather than trying to train people whose opinions contradict the employer's, as attitudes are very hard to change.

It is important to comprehend and be aware of the following guidelines while creating training programs.

1. For example, trainee waiters who are losing tips in order to attend a course may well regret the time and thus be unwilling to participate actively. Training can only be successful if it is acknowledged that learning is a voluntary process, that individuals must be keen to learn and consequently they must be properly motivated.
2. People acquire knowledge and skills at varying rates, and when it comes to adults in particular, they frequently begin with disparate backgrounds, goals, and mindsets.
3. Nervousness, dread, inferiority complexes, and a lack of confidence all impede learning.
4. Training should be provided in brief, frequent sessions as opposed to a few lengthy ones. For instance, ten courses lasting 45 minutes are clearly preferable to one class lasting seven and a half hours when teaching a trainee how to handle culinary equipment.
5. Students need to take on active roles and engage in the learning process. For instance, lectures place students in a passive role, but discussions and hands-on activities give them active roles.
6. Training needs to fully utilize all of the senses—not just one, like hearing—as well as suitable and varied tactics.
7. Trainees require specific goals, and advancement needs to be monitored often.
8. Praise should be used to boost confidence rather than reprimanding it. Education must be fulfilling.
9. The acquisition of skills and information occurs in phases, characterized by times of advancement, stagnation, and even deterioration of the previously gained skill or knowledge. Teachers need to be aware of this occurrence because it can lead to a lot of trainee dissatisfaction and unhappiness.

5. What Do Managers Do?

It is crucial to take managers' actions into account when creating comprehensive management development plans in order to ensure that the plans fulfill the needs of both the organization and the person. There are several management competencies that can be divided into three main tiers, according to the Council for Management Education and Development. These are focused on various matters based on the managers' level of seniority.

Tasks related to overseeing operations will become less commonplace as one advances up the organizational ladder, and instead focus more on organizing change and interpreting management information. Though these skills could be considered necessary in any setting, the issue of management competences also needs to be considered in light of the global and multicultural makeup of many hospitality companies.

6. Formal Wages Administration

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7. Principles Of Incentive Schemes

When creating an incentive program, whether it is for the hospitality sector or not, there are a few guidelines that must be followed in order for it to work well over time.

1. Consider cultural differences: in certain societies, certain types of rewards simply aren't effective.
2. The main business goals of the project should be highlighted, and incentive payments should be used to help them be achieved. People should be able to relate to the project's performance through these payments; for instance, if food gross profit is important, the chef and possibly his employees should also receive rewards for

meeting gross profit goals. However, only things that an individual has control over ought to be listed. For example, a chef cannot control rates or rent, so it makes little sense to include these in a program designed just for the cook.

3. All employees should be taken into account when introducing an incentive program because of the potential impact on current wage disparities and the potential for employee conflict.
4. By contrasting actual performance with projections, targets, standards, or budgets, payments should be made in accordance with outcomes. Either a group or a person may carry out this.
5. Objectives should be agreed upon with the individual or group in question and realistic, that is, reachable with a fair amount of work.
6. In order to ensure that payments are something that must be won through effort rather than something that is automatically granted, targets should be reviewed on a regular basis—at least once a year. They should also be reassessed if significant changes occur in the situation. For instance, without the manager's intervention, trade will undoubtedly expand significantly if a sizable new office building opens up next to a snack bar. Therefore, it is important to examine the turnover and other targets at the same time, keeping in mind that more work will be produced and that pay and salaries might need to be raised.
7. An incentive program should be easy to understand and simple for participants.
8. The incentive should be paid out as close to the time it was earned as feasible. Prolonged payment delays irritate people and lessen the incentive component.
9. Every component of a plan, including any regulations, must be impartial. Discretionary policies like "management reserves the right to withhold payment without giving a reason" should not be implemented by management. If earned, incentives ought to be a right rather than something that management decides how to give out at will, and the details of the incentive program ought to be included in the employment contract.

Conclusion

Like many other aspects of the hotel sector, this essay could have been much longer. An outline of the duties and scope of the human resources department has been presented to us. The person who wants to delve deeper into this field of study must realize that there are no boundaries to the knowledge and abilities one can learn. Furthermore, we need to put this information to use by improving the quality of the hospitality sector using our own greatest resources. A company's reputation with its customers and employees can be enhanced by taking care to apply appropriate action in particular circumstances. The only appropriate action is to apply appropriate knowledge of what it is that we are doing.

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